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Finding Endometriosis using Machine Learning

FEMaLe

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1. Introduction

Work Package 7 (WP7) focuses on developing an augmented reality (AR) tool designed to assist surgeons during laparoscopic procedures for endometriosis. The tool aims to visualize critical surgical boundaries, such as the incision plane, which traditionally requires extensive surgical experience. This AR solution is intended to benefit both expert and junior surgeons, enhancing the overall quality of endometriosis surgeries and improving patient outcomes. By providing real-time guidance, the system also holds the potential to standardize surgical procedures across different healthcare settings globally.

Achieving this ambitious goal is made possible through the integration of advanced computer vision techniques, specifically leveraging deep learning models. The use of such models enables the detection of incision boundaries, a task that can significantly aid surgeons in navigating complex endometriotic cases. The effectiveness of this AI-powered system lies in its ability to analyse and segment laparoscopic images, providing surgeons with real-time, actionable insights during surgery.

This deliverable, D.7.4, represents the culmination of this work package, where the validated algorithm is integrated into the SurgAR software. It provides a comprehensive evaluation of the AI algorithm's performance in detecting incision boundaries, based on the feedback of experienced surgeons. The report also discusses the integration process, the results from testing the system in real-world scenarios, and its readiness for clinical use.

2. Background

2.1. Endometriosis and surgical challenges

Work Package 7 (WP7) is dedicated to developing an augmented reality (AR) solution aimed at enhancing surgical outcomes during laparoscopic procedures for endometriosis. This minimally invasive approach involves considerable complexity, as endometriosis can manifest in various forms and locations within the abdominal cavity. Surgeons must accurately identify and navigate the affected areas to ensure effective treatment while minimizing damage to surrounding healthy tissue. The accurate delineation of incision boundaries, which serves as a guide for the surgical procedure, is crucial for achieving optimal patient outcomes.

2.2. Role of computer vision in surgery

To address these challenges, a deep learning-based computer vision algorithm has been implemented to detect and suggest incision boundaries. The algorithm relies on an extensive dataset of annotated laparoscopic videos, where medical experts meticulously label the pixels corresponding to the incision zones. This process is essential for training the algorithm to recognize specific visual patterns associated with these zones. The algorithm is built using the DeepLabV3 architecture, a convolutional neural network (CNN) specifically designed for semantic segmentation tasks. This model employs advanced techniques such as atrous convolution and multi-scale context integration, allowing it to capture detailed features within the surgical images and produce accurate segmentation maps. The details can be found in D7.3.

As a recall the annotations and detections are done in two different classes: The Treat Zone, and the Check Zone. As shown in Fig.1 as an example, the treat zone is the part that the surgeon has to treat, and the check zone is there in order to guarantee the complete removal of the endometriotic lesion or to suggest the surgeon to check the area in real-time.

Fig.1. The treat and check zones are marked in red and green, respectively.

The data used for training this model is sourced from multiple healthcare centers, accumulating a diverse set of laparoscopic videos. Each video is carefully curated to focus on the initial phases of surgery, where the incision zones are intact, ensuring that the algorithm learns from the most relevant segments. A rigorous annotation process, involving both expert and junior surgeons, ensures the quality and consistency of the labeled data. This process is explained with details in D.7.2. This collaborative effort aims to establish a robust dataset that underpins the algorithm's learning process and enhances its reliability in real-time surgical applications.

Ultimately, the integration of this AI-driven segmentation model into the SURGAR software is envisioned to provide real-time assistance to surgeons, facilitating accurate identification of incision boundaries and improving the overall quality of care in laparoscopic surgeries for endometriosis.

3. Preclinical Evaluation

3.1. Methodology

The pre-clinical evaluation of the computer vision-based algorithm was conducted through a structured questionnaire administered to three experienced surgeons. This methodology aimed to gather both quantitative and qualitative feedback regarding the algorithm's performance in identifying surgical incision zones. This evaluation serves as the primary assessment, with plans to increase the number of participating surgeons in future studies to enhance the robustness of the findings.

Video Selection

A total of ten videos were selected to include various situations for this evaluation, with each video presented in two versions: the original version and the AI-detected version. The instructions provided to the surgeons emphasized careful observation of both versions, with a focus on the detected zones.

Questionnaire Design

The questionnaire was designed to assess the surgeons' evaluations of the algorithm's performance across the ten laparoscopic videos. The surgeons were asked to provide responses to a series of specific questions, for each video. The video-specific questions included:

- Q1. How good were the boundaries of the incision detected by AI?
- Q2. Were there any areas in the video where you would consider making an incision that were not identified by the AI?
- Q3. Were there any areas in the video identified by the AI that you would not consider making an incision?
- Q4. Do you agree with the AI's suggested incision boundary (Red Zone) in the detected video?
- Q5. How confident are you that the AI's suggested Red Zone represents a correct incision boundary?
- Q6. Would you make an incision at the location suggested by the AI (Red Zone)? Please explain.
- Q7. Would the Green Zone encourage you to further inspect the area before making a decision?
- Q8. Do you think the AI-detected zones improve your confidence in making surgical decisions?

After they answered the Likert scaled questions for each video. They will answer several questions for the Overall Feedback.

3.2. Results

3.2.1 Surgeons

Surgeon's Expertise is asked by 2 questions. In Table.1 the statistics of the surgeons are written.

Interviewee	Country	Years of surgical experience	N. of laparoscopic surgeries per month
1	Denmark	20	15
2	Italy	4	10
3	France	20	30

Table 1. Information Summary about Surgeons

3.2.2 Analysis of the results

General Evaluation

The general evaluation of how well the AI detected the boundaries of the incision, across ten videos shows a generally high level of satisfaction among the surgeons. With an average rating of 4.0 for four of the videos, the algorithm consistently performed at an excellent level. The majority of other videos received an average score of 3.67, reflecting strong but slightly less unanimous approval. Only two videos were rated lower, with averages of 3.33 and 3.0, respectively, indicating some areas where the AI's performance may have been less consistent. Overall, the feedback demonstrates a positive reception to the AI's ability to detect incision boundaries, with room for improvement in a few cases. Fig.2 illustrates this result.

Fig.2. The general evaluation of the surgeries' video sequences.

Analysis of False Negatives and False Positives

To analyse the **False Negatives (FN)** and **False Positives (FP)** based on the surgeons' responses, we need to summarize their answers regarding questions Q2 and Q3, respectively.

- **Surgeon 1:** 0 False Negatives, 0 False Positives (FP)
- **Surgeon 2:** 2 FN, 2 FP
- **Surgeon 3:** 4 FN, 2 FP
- Total False Negatives Identified: 6
- Proportion of FN: 6 out of 30 possible responses ($6/30 = 20\%$ FN rate)
- Total False Positives Identified: 4
- Proportion of FP: 4 out of 30 possible responses ($4/30 = 13.33\%$ FP rate)

Analysis of the Red Zone

Fig.3 The agreement of surgeons with AI suggested zone

The agreement of the surgeons in average with the red zone (treat zone) is depicted in Fig.3. Besides the analysis of the responses to Q6 show the surgeons' confidence in the AI's suggested incision boundaries. All videos had a 100% acceptance rate, indicating strong confidence among surgeons in the AI's suggestions for these cases.

Analysis of the Green Zone

After the analysis of the green zone, we found that all the surgeons will be encouraged to inspect the suggested areas by AI, for all the videos.

Improvement Of Surgeon's Confidence

The evaluation of the AI-detected zones' impact on surgical confidence reveals a generally positive trend among the surgeons, with average scores reflecting varying levels of confidence across the ten videos. The results are summarized in Fig.4.

Fig.4. on average, if surgeons' confidence has improved in doing the incision.

Insights and Recommendations

Surgeons were free to add comments to their chosen answers. According to the comments and explanations, and also based on their responses in the overall Feedback the following are extracted.

- The AI's detection of incision boundaries has been universally praised among the surgeons, with all three expressing confidence in its ability to enhance surgical decision-making. However, minor reservations about video quality and the complexity of certain cases were highlighted, indicating areas for potential improvement.
- **Visual Optimization:** One surgeon suggested that the visual cues, particularly the Green Zone, could be changed to orange to convey its meaning. Other surgeon echoed this sentiment, recommending a slower and more stable movement of the visual cues to avoid discomfort and ensure easier focus for surgeons.
- **Usefulness in Complex vs. Simple Cases:** While all surgeons found the AI helpful, one's feedback indicates that in simpler cases, the AI offers less of an advantage. This observation suggests a potential opportunity for further development of the system, specifically aimed at enhancing its functionality in more complex surgical scenarios where accurate detection is critical.

- **Expert Input Remains Crucial:** One surgeon emphasized that despite the AI's promising performance, the expertise of the surgeon remains the most vital component in making surgical decisions. This underscores the importance of AI trustworthiness, to say that the expert should always supervise AI.
- **Strong Willingness to Adopt AI Technology:** Surgeons expressed a strong willingness to incorporate this AI technology into their routine laparoscopic procedures. With affirmative responses indicating they would use it “**always**” or “**often,**” the practical integration of the AI system appears promising. They outlined a method of turning the system on to visualize incisions before surgery and off during the procedure, suggesting a practical framework for its application.
- **Safety:** All surgeons affirmed the technology's safety for patients, indicating strong confidence in its implementation.

4. Augmented-Reality Software

Augmented Reality (AR) has emerged as a groundbreaking technology with profound implications for the field of surgery. By seamlessly integrating computer-generated information with real-time surgical procedures, AR enhances the capabilities of surgeons and improves patient outcomes. The technological underpinnings of AR-assisted surgery rely heavily on advancements in imaging and visualization, with high-resolution imaging modalities providing the foundation for the precise overlay of virtual information onto the patient's anatomy during surgical procedures.

Here we present how we have integrated the endometriosis neural network in the AR software which is provided by SURGAR company. The purpose of the integration is to facilitate testing the neural network with real world data.

4.1 Objectives

The integration process must satisfy the following criteria:

- The neural network should operate seamlessly within the software, without issues such as crashing or lagging.
- The results obtained from the neural network before and after integration should not differ significantly from each other.

4.2 Integration and tests

To enable testing of the neural network, a dedicated page within the software will be created. This page will facilitate input from either a video or camera stream, following these steps:

1. The input frame (from video or camera stream) will be used as input to the neural network.
2. The raw results obtained from the neural network will be filtered using predefined conditions, retaining only the masks of each class.
3. The final results will be drawn on the input frame and displayed on the screen.

Consequently, users will be able to visualize the detected lesions on the dedicated page of the software.

4.3 Testing Methodology

To ensure the quality of the neural network after integration into the software, a comprehensive testing methodology has been implemented to compare the results obtained from the standalone model (prior to integration) with those from the integrated model.

4.3.1 Inputs and their Associated Ground Truth

The input for this test is 42 frames extracted from videos of the surgery where endometriosis lesions are shown. The test will be carried out on these frames.

- To obtain the predictions, each frame of this set will be used as input for the neural network integrated in the software. The results obtained from this step will be considered as predictions.
- To obtain the ground truth, each frame of this set will be used as input for the original neural network. The results obtained will be considered as ground truth.

We will compare the predictions with the ground truth to evaluate the quality of the integrated network.

4.3.2 Evaluation Metrics

The results obtained from the network are the masks and the corresponding class. To compare the predictions with the ground truth:

- We look at the predicted classes and the ground truth classes if they are exactly the same.
- We look at the masks of the corresponding classes. If the prediction and the ground truth masks are similar, we consider that they are good.

4.4 Results

A few predictions and ground truth frames are shown below.

5 Conclusions

The integration of AI-driven, augmented reality (AR) technology into laparoscopic surgery, particularly in detecting endometriosis incision boundaries, represents a significant advancement in surgical tools. The thorough preclinical evaluation has shown that the system performs well in enhancing surgical decision-making. Surgeons are overwhelmingly positive, with all affirming the safety of the AI and expressing a strong willingness to incorporate it into routine procedures.

Minor limitations were noted regarding video quality and real-time visualization. The integration into SURGAR's software has also successfully passed real-world testing, maintaining performance consistency before and after integration. Surgeons highlighted the AI's particular usefulness in complex cases, reinforcing its potential for improving outcomes and standardizing care in endometriosis surgeries.

SURGAR is also preparing the regulatory and administrative tasks to be able to safely take the software in the operating room to start the clinical evaluation.

In conclusion, this AI-assisted AR technology shows tremendous promise for future applications, offering both expert and junior surgeons real-time, actionable insights that improve precision and patient care. Addressing the few remaining limitations will further enhance the system's usability and impact in the operating room.